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Research Article

IMMUNIZATION STATUS OF CHILDREN AT POF HOSPITAL: REASONS FOR PARTIAL AND NON-IMMUNIZATION

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Abstract:

Immunization plays a significant role in the prevention of diseases and morbidity and mortality in children can be much reduced only by implementation and utilization of EPI (Expanded Program on immunization).

Objectives: *The objectives of the study were to determine*

- 1. the immunization status of children admitted to pediatric ward of tertiary care in POF hospital, Wah Cantt.*
- 2. the reasons for partial immunization and non-immunization.*
- 3. the sociodemographic factors that affect the immunization status.*

Design, duration of the study: *The study was Descriptive, and duration was about 6 months* **Setting:** *Pediatric and Gynecology wards of POF Hospital Wah Cantt.*

Sampling technique: *Convenient sampling*

Subjects and Methods: *Our study included mothers of 18-24 months aged children who presented to POF Hospital Wah. A pre-tested structured questionnaire was filled by the students themselves.*

Results: *87.5% of children were completely immunized, 9.5% were partially immunized while 3% were not at all. 33.5% of the parents believed that there were side effects of vaccines. 44.5% of the parents thought that only oral polio vaccine was required and 17% considered it as bothersome. Health facility was inaccessible for 19.5% individuals and 23% face non-availability of vaccines. Chi square test showed a significant association between educational status of father, mother and place of delivery with immunization status.*

Conclusion: *The immunization status of the children was adequate and there was significant association between literacy status of father, mother and place of delivery with the immunization status. The reasons of non and partial immunization were inaccessibility, non-availability of vaccine, considering polio was the only required vaccine and inconvenience for the parents.*

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INTRODUCTION:

It is the process of strengthening the immunity of an individual by vaccination. It stimulates the production of protective antibodies and other immune mechanisms. Vaccines may be produced from live modified organisms inoculated or killed organisms, extracted cellular fractions toxoid or combination of these. More recent preparations are sub-unit vaccines and recombinant vaccines. The World Health Organization (WHO) launched the Expanded Programme on Immunization (EPI) in 1974 with focus on the prevention of 9 diseases of the childhood. In Pakistan, it was launched in 1978. Global Immunization Vision and Strategy (GIVS) was developed by WHO and UNICEF as a framework for strengthening national immunization programmes [1] and protect as many people as possible against more diseases by expanding the reach of immunization, including new vaccines, to every eligible person. In WHO region of Africa (estimated coverage 74%) and South-East Asia (estimated coverage 69%). The largest percentage reduction in estimated measles mortality during this period occurred in the Eastern Mediterranean (90%)[2] and African regions (89%), accounting for 79% of the global reduction in measles mortality. The regions that are having low routine immunization coverage are Democratic Republic of Congo, Nigeria, Tanzania and Uganda [3].

Pakistan is one of the three countries where polio transmission remains endemic. Pakistan is achieving immunization targets set globally and has made progress towards achieving Millennium Development Goal 4. But lack of parent knowledge, limited access to immunization services and poor managements are present as hard barriers in front of immunization progress. Every year vaccines for approximately 5.8 million children are procured by the program. More than 30 million children are immunized in every round of polio supplemental immunization activity. EPI is the exclusive provider of immunization in Pakistan and about 3% of immunization is provided by private sector.4

Following are the reasons due to which children are either partially immunized or not immunized at all:

- Unawareness among parents regarding immunization programmes.
- Fear of side effects and normal immediate reactions due to immunization.
- Family stress not to immunize their children.
- Vaccines are considered as contaminated with human and animal viruses and bacteria.
- Considering vaccines responsible for certain fatal diseases.

- Carelessness towards following proper immunization schedule that lead to partially immunized children.
- Parents' opinion that childhood illnesses have beneficial aspects and therefore prevention may not be in the best interest of their child.
- Parents' belief that fully immunized children are among the unhealthy and are suffering chronic illnesses.
- Distrust towards pharmaceutical companies.

The study is conducted to find out the reasons behind partially immunized and non-immunized children and the associated factors in order to find out ways to cope with these problems and to recommend solutions.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

A study was conducted at Dow Medical College, Dow University of Health Sciences, Baba-e-Urdu Road, Karachi by Sheikh A and his colleagues to determine the reasons for non-vaccination in pediatric patients visiting tertiary care centers in a polio-prone country. The results of the research were out of 1044 patients, only 713(68.3%) were fully vaccinated, 239(22.9%) were partially vaccinated while 92(8.8%) had never been vaccinated. The vaccination status showed statistically significant association with ethnicity, income, residence, number of children and paternal occupation ($p < 0.05$ for all). The most common primary reason for non-vaccination was lack of knowledge (18.1%), whereas the most common secondary reason for non-vaccination was religious taboos (31.4%). Majority of the respondents demonstrated poor knowledge of EPI schedules.5

A study was conducted at Department of Paediatrics, NIMS Medical College and Hospital, Jaipur by Masand R and his colleagues to assess the immunization status of rural children (12-23 months age) of district Jaipur, Rajasthan and factors influencing it. The results of the study were immunization status was significantly influenced by the visit of the health worker at home, social class, religion, place of delivery, and distance from the vaccination centre to child's residence, caste and education. Sex of the child, birth order and type of the family had no impact. The most common reasons for partial immunization ($n = 144$) were: Parents' 'forgetfulness' of the schedule, adverse effects observed and not recalled by the health worker. The most common reasons for non-immunization ($n = 56$) were lack of knowledge regarding vaccines and schedule, fear of 'injection' and busy in profession.6

A study was conducted at Department of Pediatrics, University College of Medical Science and Guru Teg Bahadur Hospital, Delhi 110 095, India. by Kumar D and his colleagues to assess the Immunization status of children admitted to a tertiary-care hospital of north India and reasons for partial immunization or non-immunization. The results were out of the 325 children (148 males, 177 females), 58 (17.84%) were completely immunized, 156 (48%) were partially immunized, and 111 (34.15%) were non-immunized. Mothers were the primary respondents in 84% of the cases. The immunization card was available with 31.3% of the patients. The immunization status varied significantly ($p < 0.05$) with sex, education of parents, urban/rural background, route and place of delivery. On logistic regression, place of delivery [odds ratio (OR): 2.3, 95% confidence interval (CI) 1.3-4.1], maternal education (OR=6.94, 95% CI 3.1-15.1), and religion (OR=1.75, 95% CI 1.2-3.1) were significant ($p < 0.05$). The most common reasons for partial or non-immunization were: inadequate knowledge about immunization or subsequent dose ($n=140$, 52.4%); belief that vaccine has side-effects ($n=77$, 28.8%); lack of faith in immunization ($n=58$, 21.7%); or oral polio vaccine is the only vaccine required ($n=56$, 20.9%). Most (82.5%) children admitted to a tertiary-care hospital were partially immunized or non-immunized.⁷

A study was conducted at US Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, Global Immunization Division, USA. by Rainey JJ and his colleagues with the aim of assessing the reasons related to non-vaccination and under-vaccination of children in low- and middle-income countries: findings from a systematic review of the published literature, 1999-2009. The results were among 202 relevant articles, we abstracted 838 reasons associated with under-vaccination; 379 (45%) were related to immunization systems, 220 (26%) to family characteristics, 181 (22%) to parental attitudes and knowledge, and 58 (7%) to limitations in immunization-related communication and information. Of the 19 reasons abstracted from 11 identified articles describing the non-vaccinated child, 6 (32%) were related to immunization systems, 8 (42%) to parental attitudes and knowledge, 4 (21%) to family characteristics, and 1 (5%) to communication and information is needed to reach under-vaccinated and unvaccinated children.⁸

A research was conducted at Department of Community Health Sciences, The Aga Khan University, Karachi. By Shaikh S and his colleagues to assess the coverage and predictors of vaccination among children of 1-4 years of age in a rural sub-

district of Sindh. The results were the coverage for complete vaccination was 71.9% (95% CI=68.1%-75.7%). Educational level of mother ($p=0.042$), father ($p=0.001$) and child birth at hospital ($p=0.006$) were significantly associated with the vaccination status. Mother's educational level of intermediate and above was the strongest predictor (OR=12.19, 95% CI=1.57-94.3) for vaccination. Education of parents, particularly mother's education was important determinant of vaccination status of the children. In addition, distance from taluka health facility and misconception of parents were among the main reasons of not getting the children vaccinated.⁹

A research was conducted at Gondar College of Medical Sciences, Ethiopia by Gedlu E and his colleagues to assess the Immunization coverage and identification of problems associated with vaccination delivery in Gondar, North West Ethiopia. The results were out of the two hundred and thirteen children aged 12-24 months who were enrolled into the study 101 (47.4%) were fully immunized while 64(30%) were not immunized at all. Only 38% of the mothers had received tetanus toxoid vaccination more than once. Reasons given for not immunizing a child were lack of knowledge (39.8%), social problems (38.7%) and various obstacles (22.8%), such as child sickness and health institution related problems.¹⁰

A study was conducted at Department of Epidemiology, Michigan State University, USA by Siddiqi N and his colleagues for the assessment of EPI (expanded program of immunization) vaccine coverage in a peri-urban area. The result was forty five percent of the infants were age-appropriately vaccinated. The TT coverage of mothers for the index pregnancy was 57.3% for both doses of the vaccine. In the multivariate model four factors i.e., type of house construction (proxy indicator of socio-economic status), mother's TT vaccination status, years since marriage and parents' educational status were found to be significantly associated with children's immunization status.¹¹

A study was conducted at Department of Community Medicine, Khyber Medical College, Peshawar, Pakistan by Naeem M and his colleagues to assess the inequity in childhood immunization between urban and rural areas of Peshawar. The results were the immunization coverage in urban areas was 76.5% while in rural areas it was 48.8%. Causes for non-immunization were different in urban and rural areas. In urban areas, lack of awareness and care takers/parents being busy were the main reason for non-immunization. In rural areas, in addition to

formers, lack of accessibility to health centers and misconceptions about vaccination were major reasons for non-immunization. Parents were more educated in urban areas than rural areas¹².

OBJECTIVES:

The objectives of the study were to determine:

- the immunization status of children admitted to pediatric ward of tertiary care in POF hospital, Wah Cantt.
- the reasons for partial immunization and non immunization.
- the sociodemographic factors that affect the immunization status.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

STUDY DESIGN: Descriptive.

PLACE OF STUDY: The study was conducted in the pediatric and gynecology wards of POF Hospital Wah Cantt.

DURATION OF STUDY: 6 months i.e. 1st February to 31st July 2013.

SAMPLE SIZE: 200

SAMPLING TECHNIQUE: Convenient.

SAMPLE SELECTION

Inclusion Criteria: Mothers of children aged 1.5 to 2 years.

Exclusion Criteria: Not willing to take part or not able to understand the questionnaire.

DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE:

Our study included mothers of 18-24 months aged children who presented to POF Hospital Wah Cantt during the study period into pediatric and gynecology wards. A structured questionnaire was prepared in English. The research objectives and methods were explained to the individuals and verbal consent was obtained from them before data collection. Convenient sampling method was used to select the target population for the survey. The questionnaire consisted of details about the patients background characteristics (Age, Sex, Education of parents, birth order, religion, place of delivery, family system i.e nuclear or joint), their knowledge about immunization, EPI schedule, and the reasons for partial and non-immunization.

DATA ANALYSIS:

Frequencies and percentages were calculated. Cross tabulation were done between place of delivery, birth order, education of father and mother with immunization status. Chi square test were applied on different sociodemographic factors and immunization status

RESULTS:

FIGURE.1 GENDER OF CHILD Figure showed 51% were females and 49% were male children.

TABLE.1 BIRTH ORDER OF CHILDREN

	Frequency	Percent
LESS THAN 2	120	60.0
GREATER THAN 2	80	40.0
Total	200	100.0

Table showed 60% children have the birth order less than 2, and 40% are greater than two.

TABLE.2 RELIGION OF THE PARTICIPANTS

	Frequency	Percent
ISLAM	195	97.5
OTHER RELIGION	5	2.5
Total	200	100.0

Table showed 97% were Muslims while the remaining 2.5% belonged to other religions.

FIGURE.2 FAMILY SYSTEM

Figure showed Family system of 66% individuals was of joint type, while the remaining 34% had nuclear family system.

FIGURE.3 PLACE OF DELIVERY

Figure showed Mothers of children who delivered in hospital were 88.5% while 11.5% were delivered at home.

TABLE.3 EDUCATION OF FATHER

	Frequency	Percent
ILLITERATE	14	7.0
PRIMARY EDUCATION	36	18.0
SECONDARY EDUCATION	86	43.0
BACHELOR	58	29.0
MASTERS	6	3.0
Total	200	100.0

Table showed 7% children's fathers were illiterate, 18% had primary education, 43% had secondary education, 29% had bachelor degree while only 3% had masters degree.

Table.4 EDUCATION OF MOTHER

	Frequency	Percent
ILLITERATE	31	15.5
PRIMARY EDUCATION	43	21.5
SECONDARY EDUCATION	77	38.5
BACHEOLAR	28	14.0
MASTERS	21	10.5
Total	200	100.0

Table showed 15.5% of the mothers were illiterate, 21.5%, 38.5%, 14% and 10.5% had primary, secondary, bachelor and masters level of education respectively.

TABLE.5 AWARENESS ABOUT IMMUNIZATION PROGRAMME

	Frequency	Percent
YES	198	99.0
NO	2	1.0
Total	200	100.0

Table showed 99% of the parents were aware about the immunization program, while 1% were not.

FIGURE.4 KNOWLEDGE ABOUT SCHEDULE OF IMMUNIZATION

Figure showed 88% had knowledge about immunization schedule while 12% had not

TABLE.6 BELIEF IN EFFECTIVENESS OF IMMUNIZATION

	Frequency	Percent
YES	198	99.0
NO	2	1.0
Total	200	100.0

Table showed 99% of individuals believed in the effectiveness of immunization while 1% did not.

Figure.5 BELIEVE IN SIDE EFFECTS OF IMMUNIZATION

Figure showed 33.5% of the parents believed in the side effects of vaccines while 66.5% did not.

Figure.6 FAITH IN IMMUNIZATION

Figure showed 98% of the parents had faith in immunization, while the rest of 2% did not.

Figure.7 CONVICTION THAT ONLY ORAL POLIO VACCINE SHOULD BE GIVEN

Figure showed 44.5% of the parents thought that only oral polio vaccine is required while 55.5% did not.

Figure.8 IMMUNIZATION IS BOTHERSOME

Figure showed that 83% of the individuals did not face any problem with immunization while 17% considered it as bothersome.

Figure.9 ACCESSIBILITY OF HEALTH FACILITY

Figure showed the health facility was accessible to 80.5% of individuals, while for 19.5% it was inaccessible.

TABLE.7 AVAILABILITY OF VACCINE

	Frequency	Percent
YES	154	77.0
NO	46	23.0
Total	200	100.0

Table showed vaccine was available for 77% of children while for 23% it was unavailable.

TABLE.8 VACCINATION OF A SICK CHILD

	Frequency	Percent
YES	154	77.0
NO	46	23.0
Total	200	100.0

Table showed 77% of parents considered vaccinating their sick child as safe, while 23% did not.

TABLE.9 OBLIGATION OF NOT IMMUNIZING YOUR CHILDREN

	Frequency	Percent
YES	25	12.5
NO	175	87.5
Total	200	100.0

Table showed 12.5% of parents considered not to immunize their children as an obligation, while rest of 87.5% did not.

FIGURE.10 STATUS OF IMMUNIZATION

Figure showed 87.5% of children were completely immunized, 9.5% were partially immunized while 3% were not at all.

Table. 10 EDUCATION OF FATHER AND STATUS OF IMMUNIZATION

		STATUS OF IMMUNIZATION			Total
		COMPLETE IMMUNIZATION	PARTIAL IMMUNIZATION	NOT IMMUNIZED	
EDUCATION OF FATHER	ILLITERATE	5	3	6	14
	PRIMARY EDUCATION	29	7	0	36
	SECONDARY EDUCATION	81	5	0	86
	BACHELOR	54	4	0	58
	MASTERS	6	0	0	6
Total		175	19	6	200

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	93.016 ^a	8	.000
Likelihood Ratio	45.825	8	.000
N of Valid Cases	200		

a. 8 cells (53.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .18.

Cross tabulation and application of Chi square test showed that there is significant association between educational status of father and immunization status.

Table.11 EDUCATION OF MOTHER STATUS OF IMMUNIZATION

		STATUS OF IMMUNIZATION			Total
		COMPLETE IMMUNIZATION	PARTIAL IMMUNIZATION	NOT IMMUNIZED	
EDUCATION OF MOTHER	ILLITERATE	15	10	6	31
	PRIMARY EDUCATION	40	3	0	43
	SECONDARY EDUCATION	72	5	0	77
	BACHELOR	27	1	0	28
	MASTERS	21	0	0	21
Total		175	19	6	200

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	60.180 ^a	8	.000
Likelihood Ratio	46.748	8	.000
N of Valid Cases	200		

a. 9 cells (60.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .63.

Cross tabulation and application of Chi square test showed that there is significant association between educational status of mother and immunization status.

TABLE.12 GENDER OF CHILD STATUS OF IMMUNIZATION

		STATUS OF IMMUNIZATION			Total
		COMPLETE IMMUNIZATION	PARTIAL IMMUNIZATION	NOT IMMUNIZED	
SEX OF CHILD	MALE	93	3	2	98
	FEMALE	82	16	4	102
Total		175	19	6	200

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	10.177 ^a	2	.006
Likelihood Ratio	11.057	2	.004
N of Valid Cases	200		

a. 2 cells (33.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2.94.

Cross tabulation and application of Chi square test showed that there is no significant association between gender of the child and immunization status.

TABLE.13 BIRTH ORDER OF CHILDREN STATUS OF IMMUNIZATION

		STATUS OF IMMUNIZATION			Total
		COMPLETE IMMUNIZATION N	PARTIAL IMMUNIZATION N	NOT IMMUNIZED	
BIRTH ORDER OF CHILDREN	LESS THAN 2	107	11	2	120
	GREATER THAN 2	68	8	4	80
Total		175	19	6	200

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	1.908 ^a	2	.385
Likelihood Ratio	1.866	2	.393
N of Valid Cases	200		

a. 2 cells (33.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2.40.

Cross tabulation and application of Chi square test showed that there is no significant association between birth order of the child and immunization status.

TABLE.14 PLACE OF DELIVERY STATUS OF IMMUNIZATION

		STATUS OF IMMUNIZATION			Total
		COMPLETE IMMUNIZATION	PARTIAL IMMUNIZATION	NOT IMMUNIZED	
PLACE OF DELIVERY	HOSPITAL	160	17	0	177
	HOME	15	2	6	23
Total		175	19	6	200

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	47.666 ^a	2	.000
Likelihood Ratio	27.572	2	.000
N of Valid Cases	200		

a. 2 cells (33.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .69.

Cross tabulation and application of Chi square test showed that there is significant association between place of delivery and immunization status.

DISCUSSION:

When we conducted our study, the percentage of fully vaccinated children was 87.5%, of partially vaccinated 9.5% and of non immunized was 3%. While in the study conducted at the Dow Medical College Karachi by Sheikh A and his colleagues, percentage of fully vaccinated children was 68.3%, 22.9% were partially vaccinated and 8.8% had never been vaccinated. [5]

The results of the study conducted at University College Of Medical Science and Guru Teg Bahadur Hospital, Delhi 110 095, India by Kumar D and his colleagues, were out of 325 children (148 male, 177 females), 58 (17.84%) were completely immunized, 156 (48.50%) were partially immunized and 111 (34.15%) were non immunized while in our study 49% of children were male and 51% female.[7]

The research conducted at Agha Khan University, Karachi by Sheikh S and his colleagues showed 71.9% coverage for complete vaccination [9]

Another research conducted at Gondar College of Medical Sciences, Ethiopia by Gedlu E and his colleagues to assess immunization coverage gave following results; number of children enrolled into study 101 (47.4%) were fully immunized while 64 (30%) had never been immunized.[10]

The factors contributing to partial immunization or non-immunization in our study were that 44.5% of the parents considered that only oral Polio vaccine should be given to their children, 33.5% of parents believed that immunization resulted in adverse effects, 12.5% considered it an obligation to not to immunize their children, 17% considered immunization as bothersome. 23% of parents believed that vaccinating a sick child was unsafe. While in the study conducted at Dow Medical College, Karachi by Sheikh A and his colleagues, the primary reason for non-vaccination in pediatric patients visiting tertiary care centers were; Lack of knowledge 18.1%, whereas the most common secondary reason was religious taboos 31.4%. [5]

In the study conducted at NIMS Medical College and Hospital, Jaipur by Masnad R and his colleagues, revealed the reasons for partial immunization, (n=144) were parents' "forgetfulness" of the schedule, adverse effects observed and not recalled by the health workers. The most common reason for non immunization (n=56) was lack of knowledge regarding vaccines and schedule, phobia of injections and busy professional lives of parents.[6]

Most (82.5%) children admitted to a tertiary care hospital were partially immunized or non-immunized,. There were 33.5% of the individuals who believe that the vaccines has side effects and 66.5% do not, lack of faith in immunization were 2%, and those who have faith in immunization were 98%, parents considering that only oral polio vaccine was required were 44.5% and those who do not were 55.5%. The most common reasons for partial or non immunization were inadequate knowledge about immunization or subsequent dose (n=140, 52.4%) ; belief that vaccines have side effects (n=77, 28.8%) ; lack of faith in immunization (n=58, 21.7%) ; or oral polio vaccine was the only vaccine required (n=56, 20.9%). [7]

In the research conducted at Gondar College of Medical Sciences, Ethiopia by Gedlu E and his colleagues the reasons for not immunizing their children were; lack of knowledge (39.8%), social problems (38.7%) and various obstacles (22.8%), such as child sickness and health institution related problems. [10]

The study conducted at Khyber Medical College Peshawar, Pakistan by Naeem M and his colleagues to assess inequity in childhood immunization between urban and rural areas of Peshawar, depicted following results; 76.5% immunization coverage found in urban areas while 48.8% in rural areas. The reasons for this inequity were lack of awareness and care takers/parents being so much busy in their routine/professional lives. And in rural areas lack of accessibility to health care centers and misconceptions about vaccination. [12]

CONCLUSION:

The research concluded that immunization status of the children was adequate and there was significant association between literacy status of father and mother and place of delivery with the immunization status. The reasons of non and partial immunization were inaccessibility, non availability of vaccine, considering polio was the only required vaccine and inconvenient for the parents.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

- 1) Educational status should be improved
- 2) Convince mothers to have delivery in the hospitals.
- 3) Awareness about EPI should be increased in those women who face problems of inaccessibility.
- 4) The authorities should provide vaccines in those areas which are far away from the health facility.
- 5) Health education should be given to the parents regarding self and family care.
- 6) Increase awareness among parents to appreciate the risk benefit ratio of vaccination.

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